

Lord of the Flies - A Novel in the Robinsonade Genre

Tashaliyeva Sarvara Irisaliyevna

Senior teacher, Tashkent State University of Oriental Language

Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 July 2024; **Accepted:** 04 Aug 2024; **Published:** 07 Sep 2024

Abstract: This article analyzes the novel "Lord of the Flies" by the English writer William Golding. This work is assessed as a work written in the Robinsonade genre.

Keywords: Robinsonade, allegory, William Golding, Lord of the Flies.

Introduction

By the 21st century, the appearance of the "Robinsonade" genre as a form of adventure literature in world literature dates back to the 18th century and begins with the novel "The Adventures of Robinson Crusoe" by Daniel Defoe. The works of this genre describe the hardships of one or more people living on a deserted island. It was after Daniel Defoe's novel that many works of this genre began to be created. Examples of these are "Swisser Robinson" (1812) by pastor Wissa, "Coral Island" by R. Ballantyne, "The Mysterious Island" by Jules Verne, "The Island of Dr. Moreau" by Herbert Wells, and "The Island of the Day Before" by Umberto Eco.

In literary studies, as well as in cinema, today the term "Robinsonade" refers to works that describe the lives and adventures of people who are separated from society. When the term is approached in this way, the stories about "Jungle Children" by Rudyard Kipling, the works about Mowgli or Tarzan, or the pen of Alexis Kiwi are understood. "Seven Brothers" and Knut Hamsun's "Pan" novels can also be included among these

Analysis and results. The novel "Lord of the Flies", the first of the works that brought success to the famous English writer William Gerald Golding (1911-1993), is considered one of the best examples of world literature of the 20th century written in the genre of robinson. The writer writes his novel "Lord of the Flies" in 1952. In the work, during the Second World War, a person's role as a creator is reduced to the level of a bolt of the social system, the destruction of entire nations, and the negative consequences of totalitarian regimes. "It is inevitable that a disaster will happen there," he says. "Man suffers because he does not know and understand his own nature. I do not doubt that. I dedicated my work to the problem of studying the essence of the being called a human being," said the writer in 1957.

Researchers call the genre of Golding's works a narrative, a parable, a philosophical-allegorical novel. The events of the novel "Lord of the Flies" take place on a deserted island. This island is from a country that was bombed with nuclear weapons after an airplane landed on the island with an inevitable crash. drops off children being evacuated. The main characters of the work: Jack and Ralph. Although they are both children with the ability to lead, the two are not alike. Jack is a cold, angry boy who does not do anything that does not benefit him. And Ralph is cheerful and gentle towards him. Living without adults, children want to create a society based on their own rules. Having found a large, beautiful shell on the island, Ralph declares it a

symbol of power. Jack resents Ralph becoming the "genius" or leader because he wants to be the leader himself. On top of that, he has his supporters - a children's choir. It is from the members of this choir that he forms a team of hunters. The children, who are fed only with wet fruits, light the fire and try to make a signal, so that the flame does not go out. Children do not show mercy even to animals that have children. Now they are motivated to hunt not only by hunger, but also by the desire to shed blood, increasing cruelty.

One day, Jack goes hunting and the flame entrusted to him goes out. The ship that passed by does not know that the children are on the island. When Ralph finds out, he fights Jack, but Jack refuses to acknowledge his leadership. Jack's brutality reaches such a level that he begins to kill children who do not join the hunting group. Enraged, bloodthirsty children begin to overturn the environment around them. Ralph remains alone, all his friends are killed, but he does not despair. He does not hope that Jack will return to the way he was before, but he believes that he will survive. Jack and his comrades set fire to the island in order to find Ralph. They want to get rid of it. Fortunately for Ralph, the sailors saw the burning island and saved the children.

From the beginning to the end, the novel is rich in deep content and meaning, and it is not difficult to understand them. While telling a story about children, the novel invites the reader to think about human society in general, its main and terrible problems. The struggle between Ralph and Jack is not just a struggle of children fighting for power, it is a struggle between good and evil, anarchy and order. U. Golding emphasizes that good does not always win in everyday life, and often it is realized with great difficulty, even with war and losses.

If we read the work carefully, we will find out who is the central character of the work and who inspired the writer to write such a strange work. The answer can be understood not only from the general concept of the novel, but also from its name. What does "Lord of the Flies" mean? The word Baalzebub from the ancient Hebrew language translates as "lord of the flies". This is the name of the god of the Philistines, and in Christian religious literature this god means Beelzebub - the ruler of hell. It is this creature that is the cause of all the evil in the world and is embodied as the main character of the novel. Its only evil is ingrained in the work. Children's actions are also controlled by the aggressive instincts that nature has given to humans from time immemorial. Children who are subject to animal instincts are still wild and unconscious, who are only able to kill - are reduced to the level of primitive people who are far from thinking.

Conclusion. William Golding emphasizes that the seed of such evil exists in the heart of each of us, and whether it germinates or not depends on the person alone. The novel "Lord of the Flies" reminds us of a narrative. In it, the writer tells about goodness and evil, which are the basis of our life and human existence. He emphasizes the importance of a person to remain a person in any situation. Indeed, this is the only lesson that each of us should learn, and this is the lesson of humanity. It is necessary to study it not to brag about one's intelligence or correctness, but to live like a human being.

Golding's work caused conflicting opinions. For example, the American critic Stanley. If E. Hyman considers him the most famous modern English writer, Dj. Raban called him not a novelist, but a literary mentor, and accused him of only solving the global problems of existence. Anyway, William Golding remains the most controversial writer in the history of English literature.

References:

1. Foreign literature of the XX century. - M.: "Vysshaya shkola", 2000.
2. Dostmuhamedov Q. "Writers who won the Nobel Prize", -T.: "Spirituality", 2002.

3. Vse shedevry mirovoy literatury. The plot is characteristic. Zarubezhnaya literatura XX veka v 2 knigax. "Olympus", AST.- M.: 1997, 832 p
4. Golding U. Povelitel mux. Perevod E. Surits. -M.: AST Publishers, 2014